

Supplemental Figure 1, Klassen and Reintjes et al., 2020

Supplemental Figure 2, Klassen and Reintjes et al., 2020

PUL85 (Heparin PUL)

Supplemental Figure 4, Klassen and Reintjes et al., 2020

Supplemental Figure 6, Klassen and Reintjes et al., 2020

Supplemental Figure 7, Klassen and Reintjes et al., 2020

